

Facts

Funding: European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme

Call: Increasing production efficiency and coping with climate change, while ensuring sustainability and resilience

Topic: SFS-29-2017 – Socio-eco-economics – socio-economics in ecological approaches

Grant agreement: No 770747

Project duration: 4 years

(May 2018—April 2022)

Number of involved countries: 12

Number of partners: 17

LIFT Consortium

PARTNERS

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COORDINATED BY

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Low-Input Farming and Territories

Integrating knowledge for improving ecosystem-based farming

A Horizon 2020 research project

Overall goals

identifying and understanding how socio-economic and policy drivers impact on the development of ecological approaches to farming

assessing the performance and sustainability of such approaches at various scales

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Key activities

LIFT assesses the determinants of adoption of ecological approaches and evaluates their performance and overall sustainability in comparison to more conventional agriculture

LIFT identifies critical paths toward the adoption of ecological approaches

LIFT develops new private arrangements and policy instruments that could improve the adoption of ecological approaches

How?

Red solid lines indicate connections and information transfers among workpackages (WPs); dotted red lines represent loops and feedback.

30 case studies
comprehensive range of farm systems

- **96 stakeholders' workshops**
- **Dedicated surveys:** 1,500 farmers, consumers, etc.
- **Data analysis:** National and EU databases
- **Modelling**
- **Textual analysis, GIS analysis, maps, etc.**

Co-development of **innovative decision-support tools** through integration of transdisciplinary scientific knowledge and stakeholder expertise

LIFT covers the whole spectrum of farming approaches, **from the most conventional to the most ecological**, including everything in between